

Metachanges Painting

On Datamancy and Performative Data-Visualization

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ABSTRACT

While living in a city with 10 million people a century ago seemed inconceivable, by 2018, 33 urban areas met the definition of a 'megacity.' Utilizing weather data from the Open Weather Map for 30 megacities listed by the World Economic Forum, the installation 'Metachanges Painting' (2024) plays with the materialization of meta-forms — the idea that one image can generate a cluster of meanings. 'Metachanges' in the concept of metadata refers to detectable 'changes of changes.' Inviting the audience to become performatively aware of global temperature differences, 'Metachanges Painting' contributes to climate awareness. By touching the screen to draw shapes that change color with live weather data, simultaneously triggering sound as weather data sonification, the work engages viewers in 'datamancy' — actively creating meaning from available information, akin to reading the palm of one's hand. Moreover, by exploring the art object as 'behaviorable in its history, futurible in its structure, trigger in its effect' (Roy Ascott, 1968), this paper discusses how meta-forms resulting from generative processes entangled with audience participatory actions can engage in 'performative data-visualization.' The work explores Technoetic Arts aesthetics by revisiting Ascott's 'Change Paintings' series from 1963 to 1967, and the discussion aligns with Ascott's concepts of 'Behaviorables and Futurables,' exploring how 'prefiguration' (information embedded in raw data) delineates futuribles."

CCS CONCEPTS

Interaction Design Process and Methods, Interactive Systems and Tools, Empirical Studies Interaction Design

KEYWORDS

Performative Data-visualization, generative art, climate awareness, climate crisis, climate change, degrowth, megacities, meta-forms, Roy Ascott Change Painting, Roy Ascott Analogues, p5.js, Interactive Art, Weather Data, live data sonification.

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1 Behavioural Combinatoria: the meta-forms

Roy Ascott's connection with what he labels "Behaviourist Art" goes beyond the role of a theorist or critical observer, considering his profound and visceral engagement as an artist. He shaped his ideas through exploration that encapsulated the conceptual seed for his later production on telematic art — art projects using computer-mediated telecommunications networks as their medium. As he writes in 'Is There Love in the Telematic Embrace' [1], "In telematic art, meaning is not created by the artist, distributed through the network, and received by the observer. Meaning is the product of interaction between the observer and the system, the content of which is in a state of flux[...]" [1]

From 1959 to 1961, Ascott's series, the Change-Paintings, feature transparent square panels to be slid behind each other within a rectangular framework, allowing them to be manipulated by the spectator, potentially resulting in dynamic, ever-changing compositions. As explained by the artist, "Interchangeable elements, each with an individual identity, may, by the physical participation of the spectator, be brought into a series of relationships [...]. The act of changing becomes a vital part of the total aesthetic experience of the participant." [2].

In another series, Ascott explores wall reliefs — Hinged Reliefs — with hinged flaps, offering opportunities for manipulation leading to modification. In a statement from an exhibition catalog [2] for the *Bewogen Beweging* (“Moving Movement”) exhibition at the Stedelijk Museum, Amsterdam, in 1961, Ascott expresses that, “Change is fundamental to our experience of reality” [2], evidencing a belief in the transformative nature of change within perception. Ascott’s artistic involvement becomes a dynamic platform where the observer actively participates in the creation and transformation of art. The interactive essence of the *Change-Paintings* and *Hinged Reliefs* aligns with Ascott’s conviction in the profound impact of engagement.

Through these dynamic artworks, Ascott invites viewers to actively partake in an ongoing process of change, fostering an immersive and participatory artistic experience. In elucidating his *Analogue Structures* and *Diagram-Boxes* dating back to 1962, which are wall relief constructions crafted from diverse materials such as wood, glass, perspex, and cellulose paint, the artist clarifies that these analogues amalgamate elements of behavioral analog and trigger. Ascott specifies that, “Analogues [2] were crafted based on systems encompassing association and identity or those deliberated by notable figures like C. E. Shannon, Norbert Wiener, A. G. Pask, and others [...]” [2]

In a tribute to Claude Shannon titled “Homage to Shannon” (1963) — an analogue of simple information flow — input (mode A) → noise → output (mode B), the conveyed message is centered around the notion of “containers.” *Video-Roget (thesaurus)* (1962) delineated the contexts for shapes and form references in the associated works [2]: “(a) metaforms for organic growth; (b) formal strategies (flap, wedge, split-pitch); (c) items of intention (womb/source/goal/bottle/container/umbrella/shelter/embryo) (growth potential); pulse-waveform (energy potential); claw (holding potential).” Within this wall relief construction, a “calibration unit” (a sliding perspex panel establishing a linear connection between layers of shapes) partitioned the board into two sections [3].

In Ascott’s concept of meta-forms [3], the notion was that a single image could give rise to a multitude of meanings. In creations like *Video-Roget (thesaurus)* (1962), the artist investigated the application of templates and molds. When employing the comma shape [3], it is associated with the spiral, representing the genesis of everything. The intent is for the meaning to unfold when someone interacts with it, resembling an unfurling in the womb, the pause between two segments of a statement.

1.1 A Multitude of Meanings

When immersed in the making of the “Change Paintings” — between 1963 and 1967 — Ascott was playing with ideas of pattern, and template, and his work was still associated with Constructivism and kinetics, as he points out [3]. Considering his work in transition, he refused an invitation from Lord Snowdon to be featured in his book on ‘60s artists called *Private View*. Studying with Richard Hamilton and Victor Pasmore, Victor’s constructivist emphasis was hugely important [3], and Ascott got

involved with building relief works with the theory of Charles Biederman and the visual poetry of Pasmore, exploring art as the evolution of visual knowledge [3].

Revisiting his memories, Ascott [3] highlights that, when he saw Betty Parsons’s exhibition of Jackson Pollock’s work at the Whitechapel, the contact with the idea of action painting provoked a ‘mind-shift’-driven transition. The opportunity of exploring from Richard Hamilton the world of Duchamp and associated things — when said that “in Duchamp’s *Large Glass*, you get the ultimate refinement of the mark,” — gave insights for the particular use of a calibrator, as in the *Video Roget* as an interactive way to invite the audience to play with meta-forms and, through combining the meta-forms, achieving emergent meaning. It is possible to consider Ascott had delved into a ‘behavioral combinatorial merging’ in this transition — playing or exploring the ideas of aligning, realigning, arranging, rearranging, combining, and recombining.

In his *Video-Roget* (1962) when the audience moves the red line (the calibrator) — as moving the line in an old radio in search of a radio station — meaning emerges. *Video-Roget* encapsulates many of the core ideas in the development of Ascott’s art practice, including the combination of multiple possibilities of meanings achieved via “[...] the interrelation of the panels, and solid wooden elements combined with a transparent moveable central panel that allows for ‘change’.” The artist understands that [4] The audience completes the process by engaging both physically and mentally. According to Jenny Powell [4], the dominant form in Pasmore’s *Relief Black Abstract* (1963), as an example, demonstrates a correspondence with Roy Ascott’s metaforms in *Video-Roget* (1962), considering this shape language that can be said to be at the same time organic and machinic, related to the logic of a cybernetic system that incorporates the audience in its informational trades. Despite not being dramatically physically transformable — unless for the movement of the calibrator — *Video-Roget* offers a kit of possibilities on how the work can be read, calling for projection and transformation between different registers.

Emerging from 1959 to 1961, The “Change Paintings” series came about as a result of working on some very large paintings, which were wholly gestural [4]. Ascott remembers thinking that, “[...] if there were a basic gesture to this particular painting, what would it be? What would the gesture be that was at the root of the gestures? Then I would actually paint that gesture, the shape it took, on a small panel in the top left-hand corner of the paintings, which were usually oblong. It was as if to say, this is the seed of this work.” [3] Ascott complements his observations by considering — “[...] what would happen if I had nothing but seeds? — , when the beginning of the “Change Paintings” series came to life, pointing out that there was no other option unless one of having the forms painted on transparent panels within a framework “[...] so that the viewer, now as a participant in the work, could slide them back and forth. Out of that, they could build a painting, as it were, in innumerable variations.” [3]

2 Changes of Changes: Metachanges Painting

We begin to understand that chance and change, chaos and indeterminacy, transcendence and transformation, the immaterial and the numinous are terms at the center of our self-understanding and our new visions of reality. How, then, could there be content—sets of meanings—contained within telematic art when every aspect of networking in data space is in a state of transformation and becoming? The very technology of computer telecommunications extends the gaze, transcends the body, amplifies the mind into unpredictable configurations of thought and creativity.” [1]

Aesthetic and interactive aspects of the experiments in p5.js that derived the version of the ‘Metachanges Painting’ (2024) featured in this article, emerge from the intention of exploring how freehand-generated forms in Ascott’s Change Paintings (1959–61) can be considered metaforms in a radical estate, opening up extreme fluidity to the emergence of meaning — a quality that can be exponentiated when the media is fluid in nature when we transplant these ideas to online computer media.

Exploring the art object in its total process as "a behaviourable in its history, a futurible in its structure, a trigger in its effect" [1], the interactive installation ‘Metachanges Painting’ (2024) — places an invitation to discuss how the meta-forms resultant from generative processes entangled with the audience participatory actions can involve an exercise of ‘performative data-visualization’. The work explores the aesthetics of Technoetic Arts by revisiting Ascott’s series ‘Change Paintings’ and connects with Roy Ascott’s ideas around "Behaviorables and Futurables" [1] exploring how "prefiguration" (the information embedded in the raw data) can delineate the futuribles.

In ‘Metachanges Painting’ (2024), weather data from Open Weather Map [5] from the list of 30 Megacities offered by the World Economic Forum [6] playing with the materialization or actualization of metaforms — the idea that one image can be generative of a cluster of meanings. As in the very concept of metadata, ‘metachanges’ refers to detectable ‘changes of changes’ [7].

If a century ago it was almost inconceivable citizens would dream of living in a city with 10 million other people, by the 1930s, New York City was the first metropolitan area to pass this mark [6], and in 2018 we had 33 urban areas meeting the definition of a “megacity” spread throughout the globe. There will be 2.5 billion more city dwellers in 2050 than there are now [8], and the world’s 100 most populous cities are responsible for approximately one-fifth of global carbon emissions.

Figure 1: **Metachanges Painting (2024)**, screenshot sequence 01 (weather data from 1 megacity, Shenzhen) shows the emergence of metaforms from the user’s live online interaction with the system designed in p5.js. Brush variant shades of red and the variant audio pitch, result from the ‘performative data-visualization’ of the megacity’s temperature. Image by the author.

Inviting the audience to performatively become aware of temperature differences around the globe as if ‘actively painting with weather data’ producing freehand composition using an algorithmically simulated brush stroke that refers to the fluid action-oriented visuals of Enso paintings, ‘Metachanges Painting’ (2024) intends to contribute to rising awareness concerning our impact on climate change, placing an invitation to consider reframing our behavior considering our active role as individuals and communities in fighting climate change.

According to the United Nations [9], by 2035, the world will have 14 more megacities, and most of them will develop in Africa and Asia. On the other hand, as observed by UN specialists [9], the concentration of wealth and technology within metropolitan areas means cities everywhere “could lead the way in addressing climate change” [8].

Figure 2: **Metachanges Painting (2024)**, screenshot sequence 02 (weather data from 2 megacities, Chongqing superposed to Shenzhen) shows the emergence of metaforms from the user’s live online interaction with the system designed in p5.js. Image by the author.

Figure 3: **Metachanges Painting (2024)**, screenshot sequence 02 (weather data from 3 megacities, Chengdu superposed to Chongqing and Shenzhen) shows the emergence of metaforms from the user's live online interaction with the system designed in p5.js. Image by the author

John Stevens [10], the author of "Sacred Calligraphy of the East," explains that according to the Keitokudento-roku, the Chinese Zen Master Kyozan (814–890) painted the first known Enso picture. After that, Enso paintings—particularly in Japan—became the main teaching tool in East Asian Buddhism. Since Hakuin's time, almost all Zen masters have created Enso paintings as meditation aids for their pupils and clients, in addition to portraits of Bodhidharma. Enso can be brushed on paper, written in the ground, or written in the air [10]. It is most likely that the initial Zen painting was an Enso, created for a pupil who needed a tangible object to reflect upon, a portrayal of enlightenment through visual means.

In 'Metachanges Painting' (2024), by freely exploring freehand as the way to get immersed in the interactive dynamic of touching the screen to draw shapes that change color according to live weather data, simultaneously triggering sound as weather-data sonification, one can feel the smoothness of a digital Chinese Calligraphy brush, and, by reading the visualized data as 'reading the palm of your hand,' we navigate together the idea of possible 'datamancy' (a term coined by the author) — involving the mind actively in the exercise of creating meaning from available information. Divination from 'performative data-visualization' invites the audience to engage in the effort of reframing humans' climate awareness.

3 p5.js for performative data visualization

A JavaScript framework for creative coding, p5.js [11], that uses the metaphor of a sketch, p5.js provides all the features needed for sketching [12]. All of the HTML5 elements on the browser page, including those for text, input, video, webcam, and sound, can be thought of as the sketch.

For Metachanges Painting (2024), the program in p5.js fetches real-time weather data from the OpenWeatherMap API based on the latitude and longitude of selected megacities around the world. Temperature data is used to determine the color of the strokes in

the painting. The strokes in the painting are generated based on the movement of the mouse (or hand, if using a compatible device).

Figure 4: **Metachanges Painting (2024)**, screenshot sequence 02 (weather data from 4 megacities, Xi'an superposed to Chengdu, Chongqing, and Shenzhen) shows the emergence of metaforms from the user's live online interaction with the system designed in p5.js. Image by the author

For accessing the weather data, the function in p5.js was defined as follows:

```
async function fetchWeatherData() {
  let city = megacities[selectedCityIndex];
  let latitude = city.latitude;
  let longitude = city.longitude;

  let url = `https://api.openweathermap.org/data/2.5/
  weather?lat=${latitude}&lon=${longitude}&appid=${
  apiKey}&units=metric`;
```

For using the weather data in the generative interactive design of the freehand brush strokes color, the code lines in p5.js were defined as follows:

```
if (weatherData && weatherData.main) {
  let temperature = weatherData.main.temp;
  let colorR = map(temperature, -10, 40, 100, 255);
  let colorG = 0;
  let colorB = 0;
  stroke(colorR, colorG, colorB);
```

In p5.js the audio (live data sonification) is defined by the following function:

```
function onSoundLoop(time from now) {
  if (weatherData) {
    let temperature = weatherData.main.temp;
    let soundFreq = map(temperature, -10, 40, 60, 300);
    let soundVolume = map(temperature, -10, 40, 0.2, 0.6);
    soundSynth.freq(soundFreq, 0.1);
    soundSynth.amp(soundVolume, 0.1);
```

The velocity and position of the mouse control the strokes' appearance, and their size is influenced by weather-related variables such as temperature. The program includes an audio synthesis component using the p5.js library, where the frequency

and volume of a sine wave change based on the temperature data. The sound reacts to the weather conditions, creating an additional layer of sensory experience. Users can interact with the painting by moving the mouse or hand, which influences the strokes' appearance. The user can also switch between megacities (mouse pressed), triggering a superposition of freehand strokes referent to each megacity's weather data— exploring painting with weather data for the newly selected city. Refresh and restart can be toggled by pressing the "C" key and users can toggle fullscreen mode by pressing the 'F' key, providing a more controlled immersive experience. The canvas can be saved as an image when the mouse is pressed, allowing users to capture and store emerging visuals resulting from the performative data visualization. creations

3.1 Aspects of the code in P5.js relating to Roy Ascott's Change Paintings

Similar to the opportunities for interaction offered by Roy Ascott's Change Paintings, the program in p5.js features a variable structure where the composition dynamically changes. The strokes in the painting evolve in real-time based on user interaction and external factors such as weather, echoing the interactive and variable nature of Ascott's works. Exploring how different parts of the program relate to the concept of metaforms and the idea that a single image can be generative of a cluster of meanings, the 'generateStroke' function in the p5.js program, is responsible for creating the strokes in the painting and the strokes' appearance is influenced by the movement of the mouse and weather-related variables. Exploring the concept of metaforms, the strokes can be seen as elements that generate a cluster of meanings. For example, the varying superposed shapes and patterns may evoke different interpretations. The color of the strokes and the audio are determined live by the current temperature of the related megacity. This color and sound variation adds a layer of meaning to the visuals, transforming them into visual indicators of environmental conditions.

Color (shades of red) changes related to each of the listed megacities' weather data, can contribute to the cluster of meanings associated with the artwork, connecting it to concepts like warmth, coldness, or emotional states. The additional information displayed on the canvas, such as city name and temperature, adds semantic layers to the visual composition. This information contributes to the generative aspect of the artwork, creating associations with urban environments, climate, and geographical locations. In the context of metaforms, the textual elements become part of the generative cluster of meanings, enriching the viewer's interpretation.

Some aspects of the user's interaction, specifically mouse movement, actively influence the generation of strokes, and the dynamic response to user input introduces an element of unpredictability, contributing to the generative nature of the artwork. Considering the exploration of the concept of metaforms, user interaction becomes a part of the cluster of meanings, allowing viewers to shape their interpretations based on their interactions with the artwork. The code [13] aligns with the intentional aesthetic exploration by allowing (as a system that includes the interactor/user) an interactive and generative audion

visual experience where a cluster of meanings emerges from the dynamic interplay of strokes, colors, and additional information (live data sonification).

4 Final Considerations

Maybe the behaviourist art object will come to be read like the palm of your hand. Instead of figuration - prefiguration: the delineation of futuribles. Pictomancy - the palmistry of paintings - divination of possible futures by structural analysis. Art as an apparition? Parapsychology as a Courtauld credit?"[14

Originally produced by Roy Ascott as a poster-sized manifesto in 1967, "Behaviourables and Futuribles" [14] was subsequently published in *Control 5* (1970). It is a manifesto. As pointed out by Edward Shanken [15], the dynamic field of interacting processes and behavior from Ascott's theoretical perspective constantly transforms the system as a whole, implying that, "When art is a form of behavior, software predominates over hardware in the creative sphere. Process replaces product in importance, just as system supersedes structure" [14].

From Ascott's perspective, the interactive, methodical processes of cybernetic art are linked parts of a wider system of feedback loops that make up culture. The artist further postulated that culture is just one node among many in the web of feedback loops that make up society. Thus, Ascott's incorporation of cybernetics into aesthetics suggested that society, culture, and the arts were all interdependent feedback loop systems. From his perspective, cybernetics recognizes the idea of the perfectibility of behavior, and the possibility of further evolution in the biological and social spheres, and the behavioral sciences. Automatic environments together constitute an understanding of the human being that calls for and can produce new human values.

It is possible to optimistically consider that the behavioral ritual, considered as a creative principle, can imply influencing a shift in human behavior, raising awareness of climate issues by having the opportunity to engage in 'performative data visualization' experiences. Through action, individuals can get involved or even entangled with the artifact — a relational system or more-than-a-relational-object — expressing real-time data. visualization of information becomes possible through acting.

Considering the integration of the participant with the artworks, engaging in 'Metachanges Painting' (2024) in a behavioral ritual of 'performative data visualization', the audience is invited to play with 'data-divination' of climate change, navigating information from megacities' temperature depicted in variant color and sound by reading the data 'dynamically visualized through live online interaction within the system' as if mastering 'datamancy'. The intention of exploring the concepts of 'performative data visualization' and 'datamancy' entangled in the creation of 'Metachanges Painting' (2024) implies considering that a dynamic integration of art, science, and human values is possible and desirable, urgent.

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